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Validation of the F-DBQ: A short (and accurate) risky driving behavior questionnaire for long-haul professional drivers

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ABSTRACT

Although the Driving Behavior Questionnaire (DBQ) remains the most known tool for assessing risky road behaviors among motor vehicle drivers, recent studies have raised several concerns on the specificity of both driving task conditions and behavioral repertory of certain segments of the driving population. Among them, long-haul (cargo) professional drivers constitute one of the “intensive driving” groups for which the existing adapted behavioral research tools are still very scarce.

Purpose: The aim of the present study was to test and validate the F-DBQ (or “Freight Driving Behavior Questionnaire”), a short version of the DBQ adapted to the occupational driving conditions and typical road risk behaviors of freight drivers.

Method: For this cross-sectional study, a sample of $n = 982$ Spanish long-haul drivers with a mean age of 48.5 years was used, responding to a questionnaire composed of measures on road risk behaviors (DBQ), fatigue (Checklist Individual Strength – CIS and Need for Recovery Scale – NFR) and job stress (Effort–Reward Imbalance questionnaire – ERI).

Results: Through competitive Confirmatory Factor Analyses (CFA) with structural equation models, it was found that the F-DBQ has a clear dimensional structure, a fair goodness-of-fit, high factorial weights, internal consistency, convergent and discriminant validity and an improved fit to long haul drivers’ working conditions. Also, both (general and work-related) fatigue and job stress have shown to have a significant role in explaining risky road behaviors of long-haul drivers.

Conclusion: The findings of this study support that an abbreviated version of the Driving Behavior Questionnaire (the F-DBQ) can be used to assess traffic violations and errors among long-haul drivers, in consideration of their specific task-related conditions (that qualitatively differ from other groups of drivers), with potential implications on the enforcement of occupational and road safety research.

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1. Introduction

Professional drivers constitute the most exposed workforce to occupational traffic crashes, which represent a third part of the traffic casualties worldwide (EU-OSHA, 2019), and a high economic and health burden for governments, organizations and workers (World Health Organization, 2019; Bastida et al., 2004). Recent studies suggest that behavioral issues are a key determinant for negative safety outcomes in the occupational environment, including in specific contexts such as traffic. These findings support a growing need for validated instruments to accurately assess risky driving in professional drivers, in consideration of their specific task-related conditions, as previously endorsed by occupational researchers working in different vulnerable industries (Useche et al., 2020a and 2020b; Montoro et al., 2018; Kristensen, Hannerz, Høgh & Borg, 2005).

1.1. Errors and violations (plus working conditions?) as crash predictors

>30 years after its first publishing and after several revisions, the Driving Behavior Questionnaire, also known as DBQ (Reason, 1990), remains the core tool for approaching road risk-related factors from a behavioral perspective. Professional drivers have been partially covered thanks to some key developments made by road safety researchers from different countries. In the past, some specific versions of the DBQ have been adapted for occupational groups of drivers, including a 15-item version developed for public transport drivers (Caird & Kline, 2005), an updated 21-item version adapted according to the case of professional drivers operating BRT buses (Bus Rapid Transit; Useche et al., 2017), a 25 item version used to compare driving risk behaviors between professional and non-professional drivers (Maslač et al., 2018), a 28 item version validated in truck drivers, and a 20-item version tested on drivers from a community-based nursing organization (Newnam and VonSchuckmann, 2012). Although this list of studies is not exhaustive, it does show that the available evidence on driving behaviors of professional drivers comes from different occupational groups and versions of the DBQ (see Table 1).

Nevertheless, the case of long-haul cargo drivers remains largely unattended, especially considering that their working conditions substantially vary from the ones composing the task design of most professional drivers, including those working in the field of passenger transportation. For instance, excessively long and monotonous work shifts maintained attentional demands, and excessive physical efforts may explain stress and fatigue-related negative outcomes preceding both deliberate and unintentional risky behaviors on the road (Giroto et al., 2019; Hege, Lemke, Apostolopoulos & Sönmez, 2018).

Differentiating between voluntary and involuntary risky behaviors, is one of the many methodological strengths of the DBQ and several other questionnaires developed in the light of the Behavioral Questionnaire (BQ) paradigm (O'Hern et al., 2020; Useche et al., 2020c; Hezaveh, Zavareh, Cherry, & Nordfjærn, 2018). Taxonomically, traffic violations can be understood as deliberate deviations from the practices essential to maintain road safety (e.g., disregarding traffic lights, exceeding speed limits, harassing other drivers), and are often -although not exclusively- approached as a unidimensional construct. On the other hand, errors are usually divided into two sub-categories, which are: (i) the failures to achieve an intentional outcome (slips, the “errors” it selves – e.g., performing a concrete driving maneuver incorrectly); and (ii) the attentional failures or lapses, which are also unintended (e.g., forgetting the planned route) but still can enhance crash likelihood, given its close relationship to driving performance (Martinussen et al., 2013). In empirical terms, meta-analytical evidence suggests that both traffic violations and errors are factors consistently associated with road crashes. However, their predictive value may vary in accordance with the study population (e.g., the type of driver or road user) addressed by behavioral questionnaires (Useche et al., 2020; af Wählberg et al., 2015; De Winter & Dodou, 2010).

Back to the specific case of motor vehicle drivers and regarding its psychometric properties, the DBQ has abundant evidence supporting two (traffic violations and errors – the last including both slips and lapses; Stanojević et al., 2018; Özkan et al., 2006; Lajunen et al., 2004; Kontogiannis et al., 2002; Warner et al., 1999; Åberg & Rimmö, 1998; Reason, 1990) and up to seven-factor dimensional structures (e.g., confused errors, unconfused errors, emotional violations and reckless violations; Martinussen et al., 2013). In general, the two-factor structure (errors and violations) of the DBQ is the most accepted factorial solution since it is usually found as structurally stable (Stanojević et al., 2018). However, the complexity of driving risk behaviors and their contextual dependence -associated with factors such as safety, culture, legislation, road infrastructure and the features of the driving task itself- justify

Table 1

Some versions of the DBQ previously used among professional drivers.

Authors	Location	Population	DBQ structure
Caird & Kline, (2005)	Canada	190 corporate drivers (average age: 49 years, driving experience: 26 years)	15-item (two factors: violations and errors)
Useche et al., (2017)	Colombia	540 BRT drivers (average age: 40.6 years, diving experience: 17.6 years)	21-item, (two factors: violations and errors)
Maslač et al. (2018)	Serbia	504 certificated professional drivers and 918 non-professional drivers (average age: 35.12 years, Driving experience: 14,16 years)	25-item (five factors: errors, ordinary violations, aggressive violations, positive behaviors and lapses)
Sullman et al. (2001)	New Zealand	382 Truck drivers (average age: 40.4, driving experience: 18,4 years)	28-item (four factors: errors, violations, lapses, aggressive violations)
Newnam & VonSchuckmann (2012)	Australia	248 drivers from a community-based nursing organisation (average age: 50 years)	20 items (Three factors: Errors, ordinary violations and aggressive violations)

the need to adapt and validate different DBQ versions in order to perform measurements more coherent to the actual behavioral repertory of such population groups (Useche et al., 2017; Özkan et al., 2006; Reason, 1990).

1.2. Task-related issues and risk-behavioral associations in professional driving

As previously introduced, the high workload is -along with many other threats- a typical characteristic of professional driving, but many studies have shown (i) how not all professional drivers experience the same risk-related situations and (ii) how road risk assumption might largely vary depending on key issues such as driving frequency and intensity, that are commonly greater among long-haul drivers compared to passenger-vehicle operators (Hege et al., 2018; van der Beek, 2012; Tse, Flin & Mearns, 2006). Secondly, some behaviors evaluated by the original DBQ, such as “racing” or “forgetting destination”, are highly infrequent among cargo drivers due to vehicle size, GPS devices and more constant communication with operation/control centers. Therefore, the risky driving assessment among cargo drivers must focus on the violations, slips and lapses that could be more typical from this occupational segment.

Furthermore, and as a manner of testing the convergent validity of the research tool, this study also examines the associations between risky behaviors at the wheel and two highly concerning psychosocial work factors among freight drivers: job stress and (both general- and work-related) fatigue. Stress at work was operationalized using the Effort-Reward Imbalance (ERI) model (Siegrist, 2002; Siegrist & Peter, 1996), according to which non-reciprocal working conditions of high effort (workload) and low rewards (salary, recognition and promotion) are associated with stress processes, which in turn cause adverse health outcomes (Eddy et al., 2018; Rugulies et al., 2017; Siegrist, 2005) and counterproductive work behaviors (Guglielmi et al., 2018; Ojedokun, 2010). On the other hand, general fatigue is defined as a persistent state of tiredness and loss of alertness associated with chronic exposure to situations of high and/or prolonged effort (Kee et al., 2010; Boksem et al., 2005). Meanwhile, work-related fatigue, or need for recovery, is an occupational outcome generated by demanding situations, such as prolonged driving or driving in dense traffic, which exceed the workers' physical and mental resistance and consequently reduce task performance and motivation (De Croon et al., 2006).

Several studies have documented stress and fatigue as predictors of risky driving behaviors (Useche et al., 2017; Kontogiannis 2006; Taylor and Dorn, 2005; Westerman & Haigney, 2000). In general, these studies are based on the transactional framework for driver stress (Matthews, 2002; Matthews & Desmond, 2002), which links stress and fatigue with risky driving through psychophysiological mechanisms (stress reactions) such as impaired psychomotor control, poor hazard detection, increased risk-taking and emotion-related divided attention. This theoretical approach allows defining driving risk behaviors as transactional outcomes generated by interactions between drivers and the road environment that compromise personally relevant objectives, such as moving from one place to another safely and efficiently (Matthews, 2002). When environmental demands exceed the driver's coping resources, stress processes are generated. In turn, repeated or chronic exposure to stressful situations drains personal coping resources, leading to fatigue (Matthews, 2002; Matthews & Desmond, 2002; Hancock & Desmond, 2001) and adverse physical and mental health outcomes (Caldwell et al., 2019; Marti-Belda et al., 2019; Rose et al., 2017; Dahlgren et al., 2005).

From this perspective, the evidence on the relationships between driving risk behaviors, stress and fatigue in professional drivers can be used both in the design of road safety programs and occupational health interventions focused on the well-being of workers in the transportation industry.

1.3. Objective of the study

In view of the aforementioned considerations, the aim of this study was to test and validate the F-DBQ (or “Freight Driving Behavior Questionnaire”) – a short version of the DBQ adapted to the occupational driving conditions and typical road risk behaviors of long haul (freight) drivers. It is important to remark that previous studies have suggested using shorter scales that, apart from fitting better to the demographic features of this workforce, such as age and educational level, might be applied along with other further scales measuring related variables such as driving stress and fatigue (Useche et al., 2017; Parker et al., 1998; Lawton et al., 1997).

Also, it is expectable that the fact of reducing questionnaires' length could help to decrease the experimental desertion among a study population that is already difficult to recruit, as usually happens in occupational studies addressing the case of professional drivers (Useche et al., 2019a; 2019b; Curtin et al., 2005).

2. Method

2.1. Study participants

For this cross-sectional field study, participants (i.e., long haul professional drivers) were contacted through the National Federation of Transport Associations of Spain (FENADISMER). The total sample of the study was composed of 982 cargo drivers from different provinces of Spain (18% Andalucía, 2% Aragón, 3% Asturias, 9% Castilla La Mancha, 7% Castilla y León, 12% Cataluña, 8% Comunitat Valenciana, 8% Galicia, 20% Madrid, 6% Navarra and 7% from País Vasco).

The average age of the sample was $M = 48.51$ ($SD = 7.86$) years. Cargo drivers have been associated with their companies for an average of $M = 17.32$ ($SD = 10.80$) years. As for driving intensity, the average daily time driven was $M = 8.11$ ($SD = 0.50$) hours a day, with an overall mean of $M = 5.01$ ($SD = 1.51$) days a week.

Since -as it happens in several countries- there is no consensus on how many Spanish drivers are, actually, professional drivers (DGT, 2019), the sample size was estimated through an a priori lower bound sample size calculation for structural equation models

(Soper, 2021; Westland, 2010). The minimum sample size for a model with an anticipated effect size of 0.1 (considered as low; Salgado, 2010), a statistical power level of 0.8, three latent variables (violations, slips and lapses), 8 observed variables (abbreviated DBQ items) and a Probability level of 0.05, was $n = 256$ participants. An attempt was made to at least triple this number in order to ensure adequate statistical power for the study, increasing the number of participants up to the final size of $n = 982$, after listwise discarding 18 cases (<2%) cases. Regarding gender, and as it was predictable, we found a considerable overrepresentation of male workers in this industry, with > 97% male freight drivers.

2.2. Statistical analysis (Data processing)

The abbreviated DBQ's factorial structure was tested through both Exploratory Factor Analyses (EFA) and competitive Confirmatory Factor Analyses (CFA). Exploratory factor analyses (EFA) aim to determine the smallest number of dimensions that might parsimoniously explain the covariation observed among a set of measured variables (Watkins, 2018), and were performed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) software – version 26.0). On the other hand, competitive CFA entails the advantage of testing an instrument through assessing several possible structural compositions in order to determine the most adequate and parsimonious dimensional model for the data (Useche et al., 2021). Concretely, previously documented structures of one, two and three factors were tested and compared. In this case, lavaan (latent variable analysis software) – version 0.6–5 was used for specifying and estimating the models. Also, it is worth mentioning that Weighted Least Square Mean and Variance adjusted (WLSMV) estimations were used, keeping in mind that the data was ordinal and did not meet the assumption of multivariate normality. The cut-off criteria for considering an item's factor loading as adequate was $\lambda \geq 0.40$.

The fit of the models was evaluated considering several goodness-of-fit coefficients instead of single estimators: the χ^2/df ratio, Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Normed Fit Index (NFI), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), Incremental Fit Index (IFI), Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMSR), and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA). In accordance with some of the specialized sources with most consensus on the field of structural equation modeling, a CFI/NFI/TLI/IFI ≥ 0.90 , an RMSEA ≤ 0.08 (better if ≤ 0.05), and CMIN/df ≤ 5.0 suggest an acceptable model fit to the data (Marsh, Hau & Wen, 2004; Schreiber et al., 2006). For more information on goodness-of-fit indexes' cut-off points, it is suggested that readers refer to Useche et al. (2021).

The suitability of the model was also evaluated using the strength and coherence of the estimates, plus the absence of large or unnecessary modification indices. Also, the reliability of each scale and its items were assessed through 1) Cronbach's alpha coefficients (α) and 2) Composite Reliability Index (CRI). Convergent validity was assessed through average variance extracted (AVE) of each construct, using a cut-off point of > 0.50, and discriminant validity was assessed by comparing the root square of AVEs with the covariances between all models' constructs. Finally, hierarchical linear regression models were used in order to evaluate the concurrent validity of the abbreviated DBQ for long-haul drivers, using the DBQ subscales as criterion variables and effort/reward imbalance, general fatigue, and need for recovery as predictors.

2.3. Study variables and measurement instruments

With the aim of assessing risky road behaviors, and after applying the Spanish version of the DBQ-27 (Eugenia Gras et al., 2006), an abbreviated version of the questionnaire was designed by selecting items of each original factor (traffic violations and errors – the last containing both slips and lapses). For this purpose, the full set of 27 items was applied, and their Pearson's bivariate correlations with the total scale (items were pre-selected if $r > 0.50$ and ordinally listed) were assessed, keeping reactive with the greatest psychometric adjustment and qualitative coherence to the usual task-related conditions of freight drivers. As a result, 4 items from the violations subscale (1. Overtake a slow-moving vehicle in the inside lane, 2. Deliberately disregard the speed limits late at night or very early in the morning, 3. Take a chance and cross on lights that have turned red, and 4. Slowly pull the vehicle out of an intersection until those coming must stop and give way), 2 items from the slips subscale (5. Misjudge the speed of an oncoming vehicle when passing on an undivided road, and 6. Misjudge your crossing interval when turning left/right or doing it at an inadequate speed) and 2 items from the lapses subscale (7. Fail reading a traffic sign correctly, or confusing it with another and 8. Get into the wrong lane at a roundabout or approaching a road junction) were retained. All the items in the questionnaire were answered using a 5-point frequency scale where 0 = never and 4 = very often. The scores of the subscales identified through confirmatory factor analysis were calculated by averaging the corresponding items.

Job stress (i.e., work-related stress) was measured by using the 10-item version of the Effort-Reward Imbalance (ERI) questionnaire (Siegrist et al., 2014; Siegrist et al., 2014), previously validated in professional drivers by Useche et al. (2019). EFA (all item λ s > 0.40; 57.662% of variance explained) and CFA (CFI = 0.956, NFI = 0.944, TLI = 0.934, IFI = 0.956, RMSEA = 0.059, CMIN/df = 4.403) conducted for this study suggest that the items for this scale can be grouped into 2 dimensions: Effort (3 items, $\alpha = 0.773$; e.g., I am often pressured to work overtime) and Rewards (7 items, $\alpha = 0.790$; e.g., considering all the efforts done, my salary/income is adequate). Participants were asked to report their agreement level with the ERI questionnaire items on a 5-point Likert scale where 1 = totally disagree, and 5 = totally agree. Effort and reward scores were calculated by averaging the items on each subscale, and the effort/reward imbalance score was calculated using the ratio between these subscales.

General fatigue was measured by using the subjective fatigue scale of the Checklist Individual Strength (CIS; Vercoulen et al., 1994), which consist of 8 items (e.g., I feel tired) in which the participants reported on a 7-point semantic differential scale ranging from "1 = it is not true", up to "7 = it is true" applying to different statements. EFA (all item λ s > 0.50; 59.993% of variance explained) and CFA (CFI = 0.995, NFI = 0.993, TLI = 0.989, IFI = 0.995, RMSEA = 0.045, CMIN/df = 3.012) conducted for this study support the single-factor structure of the scale. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the scale was $\alpha = 0.783$. The CIS items were averaged to obtain

an overall fatigue score.

Finally, work-related fatigue was measured using the Need for Recovery after Work Scale (NFR; Van Veldhoven and Broersen, 2003). The NFR is a dichotomous scale of 11 items (e.g., it is difficult for me to relax at the end of a workday) in which the participants answer “Yes” or “No” to the situations described by the questionnaire. EFA (all item λ s > 0.50; 54.230% of variance explained) and CFA (CFI = 0.978, NFI = 0.970, TLI = 0.963, IFI = 0.978, RMSEA = 0.052, CMIN/df = 3.653) conducted for this study support the single-factor structure of the scale. The Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of the scale was $\alpha = 0.821$. Participants’ positive responses were added together to calculate a total need for a recovery score.

2.4. Study ethics

The research protocol was reviewed and approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Research Institute on Traffic and Road Safety at the University of Valencia (IRB number H1517828884105, granted to S.A.U.). Therefore, no sensitive information was collected or allowing to identify the participants; instead, questionnaires were anonymized. Before completing their questionnaires, all cargo drivers provided their written informed consent.

3. Results

3.1. Structural Models

Firstly, Exploratory Factor Analyses (EFA) with Promax rotation revealed that the F-DBQ fits a bifactorial structure reasonably well (all item λ s > 0.50; 51.707% of variance explained. See Appendix 1). This structure clearly represents the theoretical differentiation between violations (items 1 to 4) and errors (items 5 to 8). No cross-loading problems were detected on the scale. Additionally, the EFA scree plot (see Appendix 1) suggests that both solutions with one and two factors produce eigenvalues >1. These EFA results are interpretable and theoretically sensitive (Fabrigar et al., 1999). In particular, the EFA empirically supports the need to compare the fit of the abbreviated DBQ’s one and two-factor structures. Taking into account its frequent use in the scientific literature, the three-dimensional structure of the DBQ was also included in the competitive CFA, as shown in Table 1.

Confirmatory Factor Analyses (CFAs) were performed in order to test whether the cargo drivers’ driving behavior data fitted a one, two or three-factor structures of the abbreviated DBQ used in this study (see Table 2). The unifactorial solution showed poor fit to the data, but after allowing correlations between four pairs of error terms (V1 ↔ V2, V1 ↔ V3, V1 ↔ V4, and V2 ↔ V3) according to their modification indexes. Overall, the model fit was acceptable (see modified one-factor structure in Table 2). These correlations between statistical error terms make sense because, in all cases, it occurs between items that theoretically belong to the traffic violations subscale. The two- and three-factor models showed adequate fit indexes (especially after allowing the correlation between the error terms of V2 ↔ V4, in the traffic violations subscale. See modified models in Table 2), the three-factor solution being the one with a better fit to the data.

Overall and as expected, self-reported driving behavioral factors, i.e., violations, slips, lapses, and the general risky driving score, were considerably low so that the distribution was right-skewed (asymmetric). Far from being a new finding, this non-normal data distribution trend is coherent to the previously reported by several other studies developed through the behavioral questionnaire (BQ) paradigm, such as drivers, professional drivers and third groups of road users, that also used WLSMV and similar estimators for modeling behavioral-questionnaire data (O’Hern et al., 2021; Hezaveh et al., 2018; Useche et al., 2017; af Wählberg et al., 2015).

Table 3 and Fig. 1 (graphically) show the factorial weights, standard errors and critical ratios of the items that make up the three factors of the abbreviated DBQ for cargo drivers. All factorial weights are above the defined cut-off point (>0.40), except for item 1, in the one-factor solution. In descriptive terms, the greatest frequency for deliberate misbehavior (traffic violation) was driving over the speed limit; regarding driving errors, miscalculating a turn was the slip with the highest average score; and getting into the wrong lane while entering/exiting a roundabout or intersection was the lapse with the highest frequency reported by long haul drivers. Fig. A1.

Table 2

Goodness-of-Fit indexes for the three DBQ confirmatory models included in the competitive analyses.

Model	χ^2	df ¹	p	CMIN/df ²	RMSEA ³	90% CI for RMSEA		CFI ⁴	NFI ⁵	TLI ⁶	IFI ⁷
						Lower	Upper				
One-Factor structure	233.717	20	<0.001	11.686	0.104	0.093	0.117	0.847	.836	0.786	0.848
One-Factor structure (modified)	76.668	16	<0.001	4.792	0.050	0.039	0.062	0.959	0.944	0.941	0.960
Two-factor structure	79.744	19	<0.001	4.197	0.056	0.044	0.069	0.960	0.949	0.941	0.960
Two-factor structure (modified)	63.506	10	<0.001	3.528	0.050	0.037	0.064	0.970	0.959	0.954	0.970
Three-factor structure	61.860	17	<0.001	3.639	0.052	0.038	0.066	0.968	0.957	0.947	0.968
Three-factor structure (modified)	47.674	16	<0.001	2.980	0.045	0.031	0.060	0.977	0.967	0.960	0.978

Notes for the Table: ¹df = Degrees of freedom; ²CMIN/df = Minimum discrepancy ratio between χ^2 /df; ³RMSEA = Root Mean Square Error of Approximation; ⁴CFI = Confirmatory Fit Index; ⁵NFI = Normed Fit Index; ⁶TLI = Tucker-Lewis Index; ⁷IFI = Incremental Fit Index.

Table 3

Abbreviated DBQ for cargo drivers factor/item structure. Item content, factor the item belongs to, standardized factor loading (λ), standard error (S.E.), critical ratios (C.R.) and p-values in the retained three-factor model.

Item Content	M ^a	SD ^b	One-factor structure			Two-factor structure*			Three-factor structure				
			λ^c	S.E. ^d	C.R. ^e	Factor name	λ^c	S.E. ^d	C.R. ^e	Factor name	λ^c	S.E. ^d	C.R. ^e
1. Overtake a slow-moving vehicle in the inside lane	0.33	0.714	0.207	0.099	5.351	Violations	0.501	0.058	10.698	Violations	0.481	0.094	9.132
2. Deliberately disregard the speed limits late at night or very early in the morning.	0.66	0.928	0.400	0.167	7.622		0.626	0.150	10.698		0.630	0.142	10.329
3. Take a chance and cross on lights that have turned red.	0.16	0.514	0.409	0.096	7.926		0.590	0.046	11.502		0.578	0.076	9.739
4. Slowly pull the vehicle out of an intersection until those coming must stop and give way.	0.39	0.763	0.401	0.352	5.351		0.547	0.066	10.968		0.524	0.127	9.132
5. Misjudge the speed of an oncoming vehicle when passing on an undivided road.	0.18	0.50	0.558	0.111	9.054	Errors	0.553	0.041	14.078	Slips	0.582	0.050	13.436
6. Misjudge your crossing interval when turning left/right, or doing it at an inadequate speed.	0.35	0.573	0.681	0.147	9.576		0.699	0.102	14.291		0.745	0.113	13.434
7. Fail reading a traffic sign correctly, or confusing it with another.	0.27	0.60	0.637	0.134	9.424		0.658	0.096	13.911	Lapses	0.667	0.050	15.031
8. Get into the wrong lane at a roundabout or approaching a road junction.	0.48	0.71	0.667	0.178	9.531		0.675	0.124	14.078		0.694	0.089	15.031
Risky driving (overall score)	0.364	0.402											

Notes for the table: *Retained model; ^aArithmetic mean; ^bSD = Standard Deviation; ^cFactor loading (all $p < .001$); ^dSE = Standard Error; ^eCR = Critical Ratio.

Fig. 1. Graphical representation of the structural models used in the competitive analyses, item composition, and factor loadings (λ s). Notes: All item p-values were < 0.001 .

3.2. Reliability and validity indexes

For the case of the one-factor (or unifactorial – i.e., Risky Behavior) structure, the Cronbach alpha (α) of the scale and the Composite Reliability Index (CRI) were 0.730 and 0.729, respectively, indicating an adequate internal consistency. On the other hand, the Cronbach Alpha of the violations subscale was $\alpha = 0.609$, and the CRI was 0.652 in the two-factor structure and 0.639 in the three-factor structure. Meanwhile, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of Traffic Violations was 0.352 in the two-factor solution and 0.309 in the three-factor structure. In the two-factor model, the Cronbach alpha of Errors was 0.735, the CRI = 0.743 and the AVE = 0.410. Meanwhile, in the three-factor model, the Cronbach alphas of slips and lapses subscales were 0.608 and 0.621, respectively; the CRI of slips subscale was 0.61 and 0.633 for lapses; finally, the AVEs of the slips and lapses subscales were 0.446 and 0.463, respectively. Although the AVEs in the two- and three-factor structures did not reach the accepted cut-off point for assuming convergent validity (0.50), specialized methodological literature suggests that, if AVE is < 0.50 but composite reliability is > 0.60 , the convergent validity of the constructs can still be considered as adequate (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Regarding discriminant validity, in the two-factor structure the square roots of AVEs for violations (0.593) and errors (0.640) were greater than the correlation between these constructs (0.58), suggesting acceptable factorial differentiation. However, in the three-factor model, the square roots of AVEs for violations (0.555), slips (0.667) and lapses (0.680) were not greater than all correlations between these factors (violations \leftrightarrow slips = 0.541; violations \leftrightarrow lapses = 0.582; slips \leftrightarrow lapses = 0.863). In particular, the correlation between slips and lapses was higher than the three constructs' AVEs, suggesting problems of discriminant validity.

Taking into account the discriminant validity problems in the abbreviated DBQ for cargo drivers' three-factor structure, concurrent validity was tested only for the one- and two-factor structures. A risky driving score (not discriminative between errors and violations)

Fig. A1. EFA scree plot (Promax). The number of values > 1.0 suggests a two-factor dimensionality for the F-DBQ.

was obtained by averaging the eight items of the questionnaire, and violations and errors' scores were obtained by averaging the three items corresponding to each subscale. Both traffic violations, errors, and the total risky driving score were used as criterion variables in hierarchical linear regression models. In the first step of the regressions, age, sex, and weekly driving hours were entered as predictors. In the second step, Effort/Reward imbalance was introduced. In the third step, occupational fatigue was introduced, followed by general fatigue in the fourth step.

Table 4 summarizes the regression models to predict violations, errors and risky driving. Together, the predictors of the model significantly explained 6.5% of violations variance ($F = 11.303$, $p < .001$), 4.3% of errors variance ($F = 7.217$, $p < .001$) and 7.4% of risky driving variance ($F = 13.046$, $p < .001$). As expected, effort/reward imbalance, need for recovery, and general fatigue were significantly associated with violations and risky driving. Likewise, Effort/Reward imbalance and need for recovery, but not general fatigue, were significantly associated with errors. Table A1.

All associations between predictors and criterion variables were positive. Effort/Reward Imbalance (ERI) was the variable with the greatest weight in the models, followed by general fatigue (CIS) and the need for recovery (NFR; work-related fatigue).

4. Discussion

This study examined the psychometric properties of the F-DBQ, an 8-item DBQ-based behavioral questionnaire focused on evaluating risky driving behaviors in light of the work-related conditions of long-haul (freight) professional drivers. Based on previous

Table 4

Standardized regression coefficients of the predictors associated with violations, errors and risky driving.

	Violations (V)	Errors (E)	Risky driving (E + V)
Step 1			
Age	0.111**	-0.048	-0.097*
Sex ^a	-0.014	-0.030	-0.026
Weekly driving (hours)	0.014	0.035	0.028
Step 2			
E/R Imbalance (ERI)	0.178**	0.151**	0.197**
Step 3			
Need for Recovery (NFR)	0.103**	0.123**	0.134**
Step 4			
General Fatigue (CIS)	0.156**	0.065	0.135**

Notes for the table: ^a Categorical dichotomous variable (values are computed as 1 = Male; 0 = Female); * Significant at the level $p < .050$; ** Significant at the level $p < .001$.

Table A1
Item factor weights (EFA) for the F-DBQ – rotated matrix.

Structure Matrix		
Item	Factor	
	1	2
6. Misjudge your crossing interval when turning left/right, or doing it at an inadequate speed.	0.784	0.278
7. Fail reading a traffic sign correctly, or confusing it with another.	0.753	0.243
8. Get into the wrong lane at a roundabout or approaching a road junction.	0.737	0.369
5. Misjudge the speed of an oncoming vehicle when passing on an undivided road.	0.689	0.251
1. Overtake a slow-moving vehicle in the inside lane	0.090	0.750
3. Take a chance and cross on lights that have turned red.	0.365	0.691
2. Deliberately disregard the speed limits late at night or very early in the morning.	0.331	0.688
4. Slowly pull the vehicle out of an intersection until those coming must stop and give way.	0.315	0.581

Notes for the Table: Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser normalization.

evidence on the original 27-item DBQ, one-, two-, and three-dimensional factor solutions were tested for this abbreviated version. Although the three-factor structure had discriminant validity problems, the reported psychometric results support the construct and concurrent validity of the one- and two-factor structures of the scale. In particular, this study suggests that the abbreviated DBQ for cargo drivers is consistent with the theory of Reason (1991) on the differentiation between traffic violations and unintentional driving mistakes. Additionally, the reported discriminant validity problems for a three-factor structure are in line with the evidence suggesting that the differentiation between transit violations and errors is more stable than the difference between violations, slips and lapses (Özkan et al., 2006; Lajunen et al., 2004; Stanojević et al., 2018; Warner et al., 2011).

Certainly, the reliability coefficients of the DBQ factors examined in this study are relatively low compared to the 27-item version of the questionnaire (Åberg & Rimmö, 1998; Dobson et al., 1999; Kontogiannis et al., 2002; Lajunen et al., 2004; Özkan et al., 2006; Reason, 1991; Stanojević et al., 2018; Warner et al., 2011). However, the reported decrease in reliability is due to the fact that Cronbach's Alpha and the composite reliability index are sensitive to both the quality and number of items on the scales. Even so, reliability levels of traffic violation and error' subscales can be considered acceptable according to the cut-off points proposed by Fornell & Larcker (1981). Furthermore, the reliability reported for both errors and violations subscales is very similar to those of other reduced versions of the questionnaire (Martinussen et al., 2013).

Regarding concurrent validity, this study found that traffic violations, errors and risky driving are associated with the effort/reward effort imbalance model of stress and with cargo drivers' work-related and general fatigue. These results are consistent with previous literature on psychosocial work risk factors in professional drivers, which suggests that adverse working conditions and fatigue problems are central determinants of risky driving (Hege et al., 2018; Useche et al., 2017; Kontogiannis, 2006; Taylor and Dorn, 2005; Matthews, 2002; Matthews & Desmond, 2002; Westerman & Haigney, 2000).

4.1. Limitations of the study and further research

Although this research used a considerably large and representative study sample, the statistical parameters and model fit coefficients were adequately verified, and the quality and value of the questionnaires had been previously supported by many empirical studies, some both methodological and qualitative biasing sources should be considered. Firstly, the research was carried out by means of self-report-based data, and several studies have shown how self-report measures may carry different biases, such as acquiescent answers (i.e., the total agreement of participants with the presented questions), social desirability and lack of sincerity, especially considering that most of the questionnaires were applied at the workplace, in the companies where the drivers were working.

Second, the cross-sectional design prevents attributions of causality in the relationships between variables, and the sample selection criteria prevent generalizations of results to the entire population of Spanish cargo drivers. Likewise, the effect of demographic variables such as sex, which is consistently associated with the DBQ in previous research, was not examined in this study due to the very low representation of women in the occupational group of cargo drivers. Furthermore, positive/negative affects/mood may impact the response style of participants, especially when addressing issues that may seem sensitive, such as occupational safety-related behaviors, even when responding to anonymous questionnaires, as pointed out by [Chai et al. \(2016\)](#) and [af Wählberg et al. \(2015\)](#) in previous studies dealing with different samples of drivers and their road safety-linked outcomes. Finally, and as mentioned at the introduction of this paper, even with a great likelihood and the appended risky behaviors as universal as possible (one of the aims of developing the F-DBQ), task design and working conditions of freight drivers could still slightly vary across contexts. Therefore, the following could be suggestable: (i) to qualitatively review the scale before using it, and (ii) to perform studies in further contexts in order to improve its construct validity and evidence supporting its psychometric value in future research.

5. Conclusion

The findings of this study support that an abbreviated version of the Driving Behavior Questionnaire (the F-DBQ) can be used to assess traffic violations and errors among cargo drivers in consideration of their specific task-related conditions. Regarding psychometric issues, the F-DBQ has shown a good fit to the data, adding good insights on its factor structure, reliability and both convergent

and discriminant validity.

Finally, and taking into account the common theoretical framework between the proposed F-DBQ questionnaire structure and the original version of the DBQ, it is reasonable to expect that future studies will find good stability for the F-DBQ in groups of professional drivers with increased driving intensity and greater fatigue-related risk factors.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sergio A. Useche: Conceptualization, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing– original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Boris Cendales:** Visualization, Methodology, Writing– original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Ignacio Lijarcio:** Visualization, Software. **Francisco J. Llamazares:** Visualization, Data curation, Writing– original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix 1

Exploratory Factor Analysis of the Freight Driving Behavior Questionnaire (F-DBQ)

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